

**SPECIFICITY AND CO-ORDINATION OF TREATMENT
WHEN HYPERTENSION AND DEFORMING
OSTEOARTHRITIS COEXIST**

Reviewer: Dotsent Rakhimova M.E

Scientific supervisor: PhD Khalmetova F.I

**Tashkent Medical Academy, Department of Internal Medicine No. 1,
cardiology graduate student**

Abdurahimov Asqarbek G`ayrat o`g`li

ABSTRACT: The article devoted to the topic specificity and co-ordination of treatment when hypertension and deforming osteoarthritis coexist. Moreover, the author highlighted main symptoms of the illness and effective ways of fight disease. On the other hand, basic theories of scientists and new statistics were noted.

KEY WORDS: *blood circulation, cardiovascular system, vessels, Hemorrhagic infarction, atherosclerosis, thrombus, cholesterol.*

We know that today, high blood pressure or hypertension is one of the most common diseases of the cardiovascular system. The disease is manifested by an increase in arterial blood pressure, and often its indicator exceeds 140/90. According to many experts in the field of cardiovascular diseases, hypertension often occurs as a result of blood circulation disorders. High arterial blood pressure has a negative effect on blood vessels, because they suddenly narrow for a short time. In very strong pressure, some blood vessels burst and internal bleeding is observed. Hemorrhagic infarction occurs in the organs where the vessels have lost

their elasticity and are prone to fragility. Hypertension is a disease caused by a violation of the nervous-functional activity of blood vessels. The disease mainly occurs in people over 40 years old, but in recent years, it has been observed more often in young people. Both men and women suffer from hypertension. This disease is one of the leading causes of death among people with diseases of the cardiovascular system. Scientists have been studying this disease for several decades. According to research, hypertension is one of the main causes of disability on our planet. According to statistics, if first aid is provided late when blood pressure increases, the condition of patients may worsen, and even death may occur.

The main symptom of hypertension is headache due to spasm and narrowing of cerebral vessels. Also, noise in the ears, decreased visual acuity, weakness, sleep disturbances, dizziness, heaviness in the head, and increased heart rate are often manifested. These symptoms are noticeable in the early stages of the disease. Later, heart failure occurs due to long-term straining of the heart. The reason for the development of the disease is long-term stress and depression, frequent psychological stress. Often these are caused by work that requires constant emotional tension. In addition, concussion patients have a high risk of developing the disease. Hereditary predisposition is also among the reasons: if a person's generation has this disease, then the risk of developing this disease increases several times[3]. The main factor affecting the development of the disease is a sedentary lifestyle. As people age, atherosclerosis can develop, and an increase in blood pressure against the background of this change makes the situation even more serious. This is extremely dangerous for life, because through narrowed blood vessels, it is observed that the blood does not flow to the brain, heart, or part of the kidneys. If there are thrombus and cholesterol accumulations on the walls of blood vessels, they can break off during strong pressure, clog the capillary blood vessels, and prevent blood flow. In this case, myocardial

infarction or stroke occurs. Heart failure is also included in the list of its causes. This disease can trigger the development of secondary diseases in patients, for example, stroke, heart attack, osteoarthritis and so on. The human body has a very complex structure. This means that the disease present in the body affects other organs as well. Therefore, what should the patient pay attention to when high blood pressure is accompanied by osteoarthritis. Before answering this question, we need to give a brief information about osteoarthritis.

Osteoarthritis is a heterogeneous group of different etiology and similar biological, morphological and clinical manifestations. Osteoarthritis mainly affects weight-bearing joints: knee, hip, shoulder and hip joints. Distal and proximal interphalangeal joints and ankle-wrist joints can be affected, but such localization is rare. In the development of the disease, the weight that the patient carries on a daily basis plays an important role, because they mainly affect the supporting joints. Arthrosis can be primary or idiopathic, and its cause remains unknown. It can be local (one or two joints are affected) and generalized (three or more joints are affected). Local osteoarthrosis is often associated with damage to knee joints (gonarthrosis) and hip joints (coxarthrosis). Secondary osteoarthrosis has a clear cause of the disease: trauma, metabolic diseases, other rheumatological diseases[4].

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a whole-joint disease characterized by subchondral bone perfusion abnormalities and neovascular invasion into the synovium and articular cartilage. In addition to local vascular disturbance, mounting evidence suggests a pivotal role for systemic vascular pathology in the aetiology of OA. This Review outlines the current understanding of the close relationship between high blood pressure (hypertension) and OA at the crossroads of epidemiology and molecular biology[1]. As one of the most common comorbidities in patients with OA, hypertension can disrupt joint homeostasis both biophysically and biochemically. High blood pressure can increase intraosseous pressure and cause hypoxia, which in

turn triggers subchondral bone and osteochondral junction remodelling. Furthermore, systemic activation of the renin–angiotensin and endothelin systems can affect the Wnt– β -catenin signalling pathway locally to govern joint disease. The intimate relationship between hypertension and OA indicates that endothelium-targeted strategies, including re-purposed FDA-approved antihypertensive drugs, could be useful in the treatment of OA.

Epidemiologically, high blood pressure (hypertension) has been linked to radiographic and symptomatic knee osteoarthritis. At the tissue level, systemic hypertension leads to subchondral bone perfusion abnormalities and ischaemia, which disrupts angiogenic–osteogenic coupling and impairs the integrity of the bone–cartilage functional unit. At the molecular level, systemic activation of the renin–angiotensin, endothelin and Wnt– β -catenin signalling pathways induces a phenotypical change in articular chondrocytes and triggers cartilage degradation. Antihypertensive medications that exhibit chondroprotective effects in preclinical studies warrant further investigation in patients with osteoarthritis and the frequently encountered comorbidity of systemic hypertension[2].

Summarizing the information given above, we can conclude that a person's health is measured not only by the absence of disease or physical defects, but also by physical and mental peace. Of course, rational nutrition, physical activity, timely rest, compliance with personal hygiene rules, refraining from harmful habits, productive work, improvement and protection of human health are important factors. The World Health Organization classifies the determinants of health as follows: 10-15% of human health is environmental, 10-15% is genetics, 10-12% is the level of the medical system, and the remaining 55-60% depends on lifestyle. It can be seen that the more we can lead a healthy lifestyle - eat right, be physically active, free from harmful habits, and organize our daily routine. No matter how strong the genetic factor is, inherited disease can be limited if a person follows a healthy lifestyle. For example, if a parent has diabetes or hypertension,

children should try to be free of excess weight from a young age. Then they may not develop a genetic disease or meet at the age of 70-80, not at 30-40.

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